

1 **Multiplicity eludes peer-review in COVID-19 research**

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22 **Abstract**

23 Multiplicity arises when data analysis involves multiple simultaneous tests, increasing
24 the chance of spurious findings. It is a widespread problem in public health and
25 environmental research, but many researchers, referees and editors do not consider it a
26 problem that needs addressing. In this paper, we approach the multiplicity problem in two
27 ways. On the one hand, we analyse recently published COVID-19 research as a case
28 study. We show how a striking, potentially spurious finding may bypass peer-review and
29 quickly spread through important media worldwide. A simple multiplicity analysis could
30 have modulated the tone of certainty of the conclusions reached while maintaining the
31 communication and discussion of the paper's findings. On the other hand, we perform an
32 exploratory analysis of the Web of Science Core Collection database for COVID-19
33 studies based on p-values. Of the 100 COVID-19 papers reviewed, 50% included over 34
34 simultaneous tests, with 10% including over 160 tests. Only one paper explicitly
35 addressed the inflation error induced by multiplicity, suggesting a highly likely inclusion
36 of spurious results that bypass the peer-review process. We argue that authors and
37 reviewers of observational studies involving multiple testing, especially those with a large
38 social impact, should pay special attention to the increased chance of false positives
39 derived from the multiplicity effect. We propose that authors explicitly report the real
40 multiplicity level involved in their studies, either visible or hidden, and clarify the
41 limitations of their conclusions. This good practice should not restrict authors from
42 discussing findings of interest on a per-test basis, regardless of multiplicity adjustments.

43 **Keywords:** multiple hypotheses testing; p-value; Bonferroni method; false discovery
44 rate, SARS-CoV-2.

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46 **1. Introduction**

47

48 Multiplicity is a common problem in environmental and epidemiological research
49 (García, 2003; Levin, 1996; Ottenbacher, 1998; Patel & Ioannidis, 2014). It is especially
50 critical in observational studies in which many questions (that is, many individual tests)
51 are asked on many variables measured in the same data set (Goodman, 1998). When the
52 results of multiple testing are evaluated individually (i.e., on a per-test basis), the chance
53 of obtaining false positives (“spurious discoveries”) increases with the number of tests
54 performed. On a table of ten tests, the probability of obtaining at least one spurious may
55 increase to 40%, instead of the 5% declared as the per-test level of significance. When
56 performing 50 simultaneous tests almost ensures (90%) at least one false discovery. In
57 recent decades, most researchers, referees, and editors have ignored or diminished the
58 problem (Young & Karr, 2011).

59 The COVID-19 pandemic has multiplied observational research looking for ways to fight
60 the pandemic as best and as quickly as possible (COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition,
61 2020). Although research advances related to COVID-19 have been impressive over the
62 last year, the mountain of false positives probably continues to grow, and results in the
63 generation of inconsistent evidence that complicates the development of proper public
64 health guidelines (Gutiérrez-Hernández & García, 2021; Mugnai, Paolini, & Bilato, 2020;
65 Perillat & Baigrie, 2021; Tang, 2020).

66 This paper deals with the crucial role of the “multiplicity problem” when analysing data
67 from observational studies in which many research questions are tested.

68 First, we consider a recently published case study on COVID-19, including a striking
69 discovery, reported widely in the media. It illustrates the potential consequences of
70 ignoring multiplicity in observational studies and the importance of informing readers

71 about the level of multiplicity, both explicit and hidden (Forstmeier & Schielzeth, 2011),
72 to avoid mere suggestions being presented as solid peer-reviewed evidence for public
73 opinion and to authorities. Secondly, we perform a preliminary analysis of COVID-19
74 peer-reviewed scientific literature that uses p-values as a primary tool to determine the
75 potential significance of their research. We are interested in evaluating how many articles
76 involving multiple testing address multiplicity or mention it as a potential limitation,
77 Our working hypotheses are that: 1) at least one striking finding derived from evaluating
78 the unadjusted p-values in the analysed case study does not respond to an actual effect.
79 Instead, it is probably a spurious finding derived from multiple testing; 2) COVID-19
80 peer-reviewed studies involving high multiplicity largely ignore its potential effects on
81 their conclusions.

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83 **2. Methods**

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85 **2.1. Background**

86 The p-value approach to hypothesis testing involves comparing the probability of
87 observing the calculated test statistics under the null hypothesis (p-value), with a fixed
88 threshold, alpha, usually 0.05 or 0.01. The result is significant (i.e., the null hypothesis is
89 rejected) if the obtained p-value is lower than (or equal to) alpha. Otherwise, the null
90 hypothesis is not rejected, and the result is considered “non-significant”. This procedure
91 has been used for almost the last hundred years, mainly since R. A. Fisher provided the
92 means to calculate the p-value in a wide variety of situations (Brereton, 2020; Fisher,
93 1925).

94 When the required assumptions of the statistical procedure used are met, the probability
95 of obtaining at least one significant spurious result (that is, rejecting the null hypothesis
96 being true, type I error) is controlled at the fixed threshold. However, this is not true when
97 several or many (n) simultaneous independent tests are carried out since, as mentioned
98 above, the overall type I error can overgrow up to 40 ($n = 10$) or 90% ($n = 50$). It is,
99 therefore, necessary to apply specific procedures to control for type I error inflation when
100 performing multiple tests.

101 There are two main approaches to handle multiple testing: controlling the type I error rate
102 per table or family (Familywise Error Rate, FWER), that is, the probability of having one
103 or more false positives in the whole set; and controlling the false discovery rate (FDR),
104 that is, the expected proportion of spurious rejections among the whole rejections
105 (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995). In recent decades, there has been much controversy on
106 this issue (Farcomeni, 2008; Dirnagl, 2019; Amrhein, Greenland & McShane, 2019). This
107 controversy involves those who defend trying to limit the spurious findings derived from
108 multiple testing against those defending the idea that even not replicated striking results
109 with a high probability of being spurious should be freely published, given that
110 subsequent investigations may already reveal erroneous conclusions.

111 Many previous studies have already addressed the multiplicity issue, called attention to
112 its potential consequences (García, 2004; Young, Bang & Oktay, 2009; Young & Karr,
113 2011; Forstmeier, Wagenmakers & Parker, 2017) and explained the fundamental
114 theoretical issues and main calculation algorithms (Shaffer, 1995; Krzywinski and
115 Altman, 2014). Hence, we will not expand the topic further.

116

117 2.2. A COVID-19 case study

118 We use a paper recently published (Rodríguez-Barranco et al., 2021) as a case study. This
119 article has had a widespread diffusion since it was first published in early view several
120 months ago. Televisions, newspapers, and social networks around the world echoed its
121 alarming discovery: walking a dog increased your risk of getting COVID-19 by nearly
122 80% (see, for example, ABC7 News Staff, 2020). Even today, internet search engines
123 will return hundreds of results to connect COVID-19 and dog walking. This article, which
124 stands out in the [PlumX metrics](#) (mainly in Mentions and Social Media diffusion metrics),
125 is an excellent example of a paper published in a rigorous peer-reviewed journal that
126 includes an isolated (non-replicated) striking discovery with high social impact.

127 Rodríguez-Barranco et al. (2021) performed an online survey to identify risk factors for
128 contracting COVID-19. They tested differences in the estimated prevalence of COVID-
129 19 between categories of the variables studied and concluded that only six out of the >40
130 used single predictors were significantly related to differences in COVID-19 prevalence.
131 These were living with a COVID-19 patient ($p=0.001$), smoking ($p=0.003$), disinfecting
132 purchased products upon arrival at home ($p=0.004$), using public transportation
133 ($p=0.007$), walking with pets ($p=0.024$), and working on-site at the workplace during
134 confinement ($p=0.030$). They also fitted a multivariate risk logistic regression model,
135 using a backward variable selection procedure on a previously selected subset of
136 predictors. The final fitted significant model retained five predictors (see Table 5 from
137 Rodríguez-Barranco et al. 2021), including walking a pet ($p=0.037$). They reported that
138 their results demonstrated that walking a pet significantly increases the risk of contracting
139 COVID-19 by 78%.

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141 2.2.1. Multiplicity analysis

142 We used different procedures belonging to the two conceptual approaches mentioned
143 above to control for spurious findings. To control the Familywise Error Rate (FWER),
144 we used both the original one-step Bonferroni correction (Bonferroni, 1935) and a more
145 powerful sequential procedure (Holm, 1979). We also controlled for the False Discovery
146 Rate (FDR), according to Benjamini & Hochberg (1995), using the *p.adjust()* function of
147 the R Stats Package (R Core Team, 2020).

148 Rodríguez-Barranco et al. (2021) selected the predictors for the multivariate analysis by
149 looking at the bivariate analysis results. Nineteen predictors with $p < 0.20$ were selected.
150 Multiple testing was undertaken to discard the predictors whose coefficients have an
151 associated Wald test p-value exceeding 0.10 and to fit the definitive 5-predictor model
152 (Table 5, in Rodríguez-Barranco et al. 2021).

153 Backward predictor selection involves “hidden” multiple testing (Forstmeier &
154 Schielzeth, 2011; Mundry & Nunn, 2009; Young & Karr, 2011), but it cannot be
155 thoroughly evaluated here due to a lack of data. Nevertheless, it can be assumed that at
156 least 19 tests were performed in model selection. As an approximation of the potential
157 effects of this “hidden multiplicity” on model coefficient significance, we calculated the
158 adjusted p-values for the finally fitted coefficients using the option for partially unknown
159 p-values sets available in the function *p.adjust()* of the Stats R package (R Core Team,
160 2020).

161

162 2.3. Multiplicity analysis in COVID-19 peer-reviewed research

163 To explore the potential extent of the uncorrected multiplicity, we explored the Web of
164 Science Core Collection for articles including COVID-19 or SARS-COV-2 in their
165 abstracts, together with explicit reference to p-values directly related to the significance

166 of the results obtained. We also included a reference to correlation analysis in the search
167 since it is well-known that exploring large correlation matrixes is a frequent source of
168 type I inflation (Rice, 1989). We recovered 624 references which were ranked in
169 descending order, according to their citations. After eliminating five review papers, the
170 most cited 100 papers were selected for further in-depth analysis (see supplementary
171 material).

172 For each reviewed paper, we annotated the number of p-values and looked for some
173 reference to multiplicity, including methods for controlling its effects or mentioning the
174 potential resulting limitations.

175

176 **3. Results**

177 **3.1. Case study**

178 Table 1 summarises the multiplicity analysis of the p-values resulting from the bivariate
179 analyses performed in Rodríguez-Barranco et al. (2021) (see Tables 1 to 4 from
180 Rodríguez-Barranco et al. 2021). As shown in Table 1, when considering the results of
181 either the FWER or FDR approaches, it can be concluded that the only strong (significant)
182 signal emerging from the whole explored bivariate relationships with COVID-19
183 presence is “living with a COVID-19 patient”. No other relationship remained significant
184 after correcting for multiplicity effects. It can also be concluded from the multivariate
185 analysis (Table 2) that only the corrected p-values associated with “living with a COVID-
186 19 patient” may be significant at the selected overall error rate (0.05).

187 These results suggest that the significant effect of walking the pet on COVID-19
188 transmission may be spurious.

189

190 **TABLE 1:** Unadjusted p-values corresponding to the bivariate tests, which were declared
 191 significant, at the 0.05 level, in Tables 1 to 4 in Rodríguez-Barranco et al. (2021).
 192 Adjusted p-values were obtained after controlling for the family-wise error rate (FWER,
 193 Type I error) or false discovery rate (FDR, expected proportion of false rejections to total
 194 rejections) at the 0.05 level. Three different correction methods were considered:
 195 Bonferroni (1935), Holm (1979) and Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) (labelled BH in the
 196 table). Significant p-values, according to the different criteria, are enhanced in bold. P-
 197 value adjustment was performed using the *p.adjust* R function (R Core Team, 2020).
 198
 199

	Unadjusted	FWER adjusted		FDR adj. BH
		Bonferroni	Holm	
Live with a COVID-19 patient	0.001	0.043	0.043	0.043
Smoke	0.003	0.129	0.126	0.057
Product disinfection	0.004	0.172	0.164	0.057
Use of public transportation	0.007	0.301	0.280	0.075
Walk the pet	0.024	1.000	0.936	0.206
Work on site	0.030	1.000	1.000	0.215

201 **TABLE 2:** Unadjusted p-values correspond to the predictors selected as significant in
 202 Rodríguez-Barranco et al. (2021), after applying a backward variable selection procedure
 203 to a preselected subset of 19 predictors with $p < 0.20$ in the prior bivariate analysis.
 204 Adjusted p-values were obtained after controlling the familywise error rate (FWER, Type
 205 I error) or the False Discovery Rate (FDR, expected proportion of false rejections to total
 206 rejections), at the 0.05 level. Three different correction methods were considered,
 207 Bonferroni (1935), Holm (1979), and Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) (labelled BH in
 208 the table). Significant p-values, according to the different criteria, are enhanced in bold.
 209 P-value adjustment was performed using the *p.adjust* R function (R Core Team, 2020).
 210 (*the original value of $p < 0.001$ was substituted by $p = 0.00049$ in the calculations).
 211

	Unadjusted	FWER adjusted		FDR adjusted
		Bonferroni	Holm	BH
Living with a COVID-19 patient	0.000*	0,009	0,009	0,009
Disinfection of food products	0,009	0,171	0,162	0,086
Traveling to the workplace	0,028	0,532	0,476	0,176
Pet walk	0,037	0,703	0,592	0,176
Food purchase modality	0,056	1,000	0,840	0,213

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215 **3.2. Multiplicity in peer-reviewed research on COVID-19**

216 Of the 100 COVID-19 papers reviewed, half of them included at least 34 p-values, 25%
 217 included over 76 tests, and 10% included over 163 tests (fig. 1, upper). The corresponding
 218 numbers for significant p-values (i.e., with $p < 0.05$) were 14, 34 and 87, respectively
 219 (fig. 1, lower). The number of the significant tests was positively correlated with the total
 220 number of tests performed (Spearman $r = 0.88$, $p < 0.001$).

221 Regarding the abstracts, the median value for both the total and the significant number of
222 p-values was three. Except in one case, none of the revised papers using large numbers
223 of p-values explicitly applied any procedure to control table-wise type I error inflation.

224

225 **4. Discussion**

226 A crucial outcome of our research is that the potential effects of even extreme multiplicity
227 on the significance of published COVID-19 results have been completely ignored, not
228 only by the authors but also by referees and editors of influential peer-reviewed journals.

229 The results of our case study suggest that, after considering the effects of multiplicity, the
230 Rodríguez-Barranco et al. (2021) study was very adventurous to offer a conclusion that
231 stated: “*The results of this study demonstrate that living with dogs, working on-site,*
232 *purchasing essential commodities by using home delivery service, and especially living*
233 *with a COVID-19 patient have been the main routes of transmission of SARS-CoV-2*
234 *during the most restrictive period of confinement in Spain”.*

235 Many other non-replicated outstanding discoveries have been reported from
236 observational studies (Benjamin et al., 2018; Ioannidis, 2005; Young et al., 2009; Young
237 & Karr, 2011). This is not surprising given that the potential effect of dozens or even
238 hundreds of simultaneous tests on the probability of having isolated spurious discoveries
239 is largely ignored. As our results show, the larger the p-values set, the larger tend to be
240 the number of significant ($p < 0.05$) results. If the problem is ignored, several or many of
241 those significant results may be false discoveries.

242

243 **FIG. 1.** Distribution of the number of p-values per paper found in 100 peer-reviewed
244 papers recovered from Web of Science Core Collection database (see methods and
245 supplementary material). X-axis represents the surveyed research papers ranked in
246 decreasing order of multiplicity (number of p-values). Upper: Y-axis represents total
247 counts of p-values. Lower: Y-axis refers to the number of significant p-values ($p < 0.05$).
248 Y-axes have been log-transformed to improve visibility.

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250

251 **4.1. A word of caution on spurious findings**

252 Throughout the COVID-19 crisis, research institutions, publishers, and scientists have
253 done their best to enable promising proposals, advances, and achievements to reach the
254 health authorities, the media, and society, as soon as possible (Dong, Du, & Gardner,
255 2020). There have been impressive cooperative advances in many research areas and a
256 massive number of papers, most of which provide valuable information, although not
257 always well interpreted (Barua, Barua, Aktar, Kabir, & Li, 2020).

258 Never have so many people, or non-specialised journalists used the terms significant/not
259 significant, subjected (or not) to peer review, and frequently refer to the conclusions
260 reliability, relevance, or provisional nature of the published results (Bavel et al., 2020).

261 Unfortunately, until now, multiplicity has not benefited from these advances, and the
262 media, public, and scientists are not interested in its potential effects on multiplying the
263 chance appearance of striking but false discoveries. The critical consequence of those
264 false discoveries may be the loss of science's prestige and credibility, which it took so
265 long to establish (Gill, Kinslow, McKenney, & Elkbuli, 2020; Lep, Babnik, & Hacin
266 Beyazoglu, 2020; Mainous, 2020).

267 The constant repetition of incredible achievements that put society on guard and turn out
268 to be spurious do enormous damage, and becomes confused with the uncertainty inherent
269 in science (Krzywinski & Altman, 2013).

270

271 **4.2. An armistice proposal in the p-war: discuss freely, but inform about**
272 **multiplicity**

273 The p-value is a widely used inferential statistic to test hypotheses (Benjamini, 2016;
274 Benjamini & Zeevi, 2020). Dropping p-value hypothesis testing because of its limitations

275 is unlikely (Lu & Belitskaya-Levy, 2015). Nevertheless, interpreting the p-value requires
276 a proper context (Betensky, 2019), and understanding the limitations and variability of p-
277 values is also crucial for interpreting results correctly (Wasserstein & Lazar, 2016).
278 Our preliminary results have shown that, even in studies with high levels of multiplicity,
279 the authors ignore the potential effects of it on the “highly significant” discoveries made.
280 Abstracts from the reviewed 100 papers included a median of 3 significant p-values
281 accompanying the most relevant results of the paper. Without information on the
282 multiplicity degree of the entire study, the reader would be oblivious to whether those p-
283 values would remain significant after correction for alpha inflation.
284 For this reason, particularly in a time of the near-instantaneous communication of
285 scientific results, the authors of exploratory observational studies with unexpected
286 striking results should be required to report at least the level of multiplicity involved, the
287 methods used to control it, and what consequences it could have on interpreting the results
288 of multiple tests p-values. It does not hurt the authors to discuss the results based on
289 unadjusted p-values but without ignoring the real multiplicity context in which they do
290 so.

291

292 **5. Conclusions**

293 Multiplicity is a common issue in observational studies. Our results have shown that of
294 the 100 COVID related paper reviewed here, 50% included over 34 simultaneous tests,
295 with 10% including over 160 tests. Only one of the 100 papers addressed the inflation
296 error induced by multiplicity, leading to a highly likely inclusion of spurious results that
297 bypass the peer-review process.

298 As shown here, being oblivious to the multiplicity issue can cause potentially spurious
299 findings making the headline an issue that is further fostered if the findings are striking
300 and media attractive.

301 We argue that authors and reviewers of observational studies involving multiple testing,
302 especially those with a large social impact, should pay special attention to the increased
303 chance of false positives derived from the multiplicity effect.

304

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Used?	Source	DOI
YES	JOURNAL OF TRAVEL MEDICINE	10.1093/jtm/taaa037
YES	THROMBOSIS AND HAEMOSTASIS	10.1055/s-0040-1710018
YES	INVESTIGATIVE RADIOLOGY	10.1097/RLI.0000000000000670
YES	BRITISH JOURNAL OF HAEMATOLOGY	10.1111/bjh.16659
YES	INVESTIGATIVE RADIOLOGY	10.1097/RLI.0000000000000674
YES	MEDECINE ET MALADIES INFECTIEUSES	10.1016/j.medmal.2020.03.007
YES	LANCET HAEMATOLOGY	10.1016/S2352-3026(20)30216-7
YES	EMERGING MICROBES & INFECTIONS	10.1080/22221751.2020.1770129
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MENTAL HEALTH AND ADDICTION	10.1007/s11469-020-00289-x
NO	POLISH ARCHIVES OF INTERNAL MEDICINE-POLSKIE ARCHIWUM MEI	10.20452/pamw.15272
YES	CLINICA CHIMICA ACTA	10.1016/j.cca.2020.06.026
YES	VIRAL IMMUNOLOGY	10.1089/vim.2020.0062
YES	INTERNATIONAL FORUM OF ALLERGY & RHINOLOGY	10.1002/alr.22580
YES	INFECTION	10.1007/s15010-020-01427-2
YES	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL MICROBIOLOGY	10.1128/JCM.02107-20
YES	STROKE	10.1161/STROKEAHA.120.030373
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF GYNECOLOGY & OBSTETRICS	10.1002/ijgo.13165
YES	FRONTIERS IN PSYCHOLOGY	10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01168
YES	EUROPEAN RADIOLOGY	10.1007/s00330-020-07033-y
YES	JOURNAL OF HUMAN GENETICS	10.1038/s10038-020-0808-9
YES	NUTRIENTS	10.3390/nu12072016
YES	DENTAL AND MEDICAL PROBLEMS	10.17219/dmp/119743
YES	EUROPEAN HEART JOURNAL	10.1093/eurheartj/ehaa508
YES	JOURNAL OF THROMBOSIS AND THROMBOLYSIS	10.1007/s11239-020-02171-y
YES	BRAIN BEHAVIOR AND IMMUNITY	10.1016/j.bbi.2020.05.038
NO	JOURNAL OF INFECTION AND PUBLIC HEALTH	10.1016/j.jiph.2020.06.021
YES	JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	10.1093/pubmed/fdaa070
YES	JOURNAL OF COMMUNITY HEALTH	10.1007/s10900-020-00881-1
YES	RESPIRATORY RESEARCH	10.1186/s12931-020-01429-6
YES	JOURNAL OF MICROBIOLOGY IMMUNOLOGY AND INFECTION	10.1016/j.jmii.2020.03.026
YES	JOURNAL OF ENDOCRINOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION	10.1007/s40618-020-01370-x
YES	JOURNAL OF INTENSIVE CARE	10.1186/s40560-020-00466-z
YES	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ROENTGENOLOGY	10.2214/AJR.20.23078
YES	RADIOLOGIA MEDICA	10.1007/s11547-020-01232-9
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES	10.1016/j.ijid.2020.05.076
NO	QUANTITATIVE IMAGING IN MEDICINE AND SURGERY	10.21037/qims-20-564
YES	PLOS ONE	10.1371/journal.pone.0239252
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	10.7150/ijms.46614
YES	CUREUS	10.7759/cureus.7923
YES	THYROID	10.1089/thy.2020.0363
YES	LEUKEMIA	10.1038/s41375-020-0911-0
YES	BMC INFECTIOUS DISEASES	10.1186/s12879-020-05128-x
YES	BIOMED RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	10.1155/2020/6159720
YES	JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS	10.1016/j.jpha.2020.03.004
YES	RESPIRATION	10.1159/000509223
NO	INFECTIOUS DISEASES AND THERAPY	10.1007/s40121-020-00324-3
YES	ENVIRONMENT DEVELOPMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY	10.1007/s10668-020-00878-9
YES	RESPIRATORY RESEARCH	10.1186/s12931-020-01428-7
YES	JOURNAL OF PERINATAL MEDICINE	10.1515/jpm-2020-0182
YES	NUTRIENTS	10.3390/nu12072098
YES	AEROSOL AND AIR QUALITY RESEARCH	10.4209/aaqr.2020.05.0218
YES	GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS	10.1029/2020GL088533
YES	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ENDOCRINOLOGY	10.1530/EJE-20-0335

YES	ELECTRONIC JOURNAL OF GENERAL MEDICINE	10.29333/ejgm/8223
YES	BIOSCIENCE TRENDS	10.5582/bst.2020.03086
YES	THERANOSTICS	10.7150/thno.46569
YES	SLEEP MEDICINE	10.1016/j.sleep.2020.05.018
YES	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF HEART FAILURE	10.1002/ejhf.1990
YES	CLINICA CHIMICA ACTA	10.1016/j.cca.2020.06.012
YES	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OTOLARYNGOLOGY	10.1016/j.amjoto.2020.102612
YES	AGING-US	
YES	ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS AND CHEMOTHERAPY	10.1128/AAC.01177-20
YES	JOURNAL OF OTOLARYNGOLOGY-HEAD & NECK SURGERY	10.1186/s40463-020-00449-y
YES	ENVIRONMENT DEVELOPMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY	10.1007/s10668-020-00849-0
YES	BMC PUBLIC HEALTH	10.1186/s12889-020-09392-z
YES	ANNALS OF INTENSIVE CARE	10.1186/s13613-020-00716-1
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MENTAL HEALTH AND ADDICTION	10.1007/s11469-020-00355-4
YES	EUROPEAN REVIEW FOR MEDICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL SCIENC	10.26355/eurrev_202009_22874
YES	JOURNAL OF AFFECTIVE DISORDERS	10.1016/j.jad.2020.06.047
YES	JOURNAL OF PSYCHIATRIC RESEARCH	10.1016/j.jpsychires.2020.06.022
YES	INTENSIVE CARE MEDICINE	10.1007/s00134-020-06229-6
YES	ACS CHEMICAL NEUROSCIENCE	10.1021/acchemneuro.0c00447
YES	VACCINES	10.3390/vaccines8030378
YES	INFECTIOUS DISEASES OF POVERTY	10.1186/s40249-020-00703-5
NO	ERJ OPEN RESEARCH	10.1183/23120541.00260-2020
YES	FRONTIERS IN PSYCHIATRY	10.3389/fpsyt.2020.00751
YES	CLINICA CHIMICA ACTA	10.1016/j.cca.2020.04.020
YES	EXPERIMENTAL HEMATOLOGY & ONCOLOGY	10.1186/s40164-020-00172-4
YES	EUROPEAN RADIOLOGY	10.1007/s00330-020-07013-2
YES	EMERGING MICROBES & INFECTIONS	10.1080/22221751.2020.1771219
YES	SHOCK	10.1097/SHK.0000000000001562
YES	JOURNAL OF AFFECTIVE DISORDERS	10.1016/j.jad.2020.06.035
YES	JOURNAL OF INFECTION AND PUBLIC HEALTH	10.1016/j.jiph.2020.05.029
YES	INFECTIOUS DISEASES OF POVERTY	10.1186/s40249-020-00723-1
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MENTAL HEALTH AND ADDICTION	10.1007/s11469-020-00371-4
YES	RESPIRATORY RESEARCH	10.1186/s12931-020-01427-8
YES	WESTERN JOURNAL OF EMERGENCY MEDICINE	10.5811/westjem.2020.5.47780
YES	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL MEDICINE	10.3390/jcm9061781
YES	JOURNAL OF AUTOIMMUNITY	10.1016/j.jaut.2020.102560
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES	10.1016/j.ijid.2020.09.014
YES	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UN	10.1073/pnas.2010540117
YES	JOURNAL OF INFECTION	10.1016/j.jinf.2020.08.013
YES	CLINICAL MEDICINE	10.7861/clinmed.2020-0346
YES	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL VIROLOGY	10.1016/j.jcv.2020.104542
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YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUI	10.3390/ijerph17145170
YES	WORLD JOURNAL OF EMERGENCY SURGERY	10.1186/s13017-020-00323-2
YES	JOURNAL OF TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE	10.1186/s12967-020-02418-5
YES	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUI	10.3390/ijerph17113903
YES	MEDICAL SCIENCE MONITOR	10.12659/MSM.925669
YES	CLINICA CHIMICA ACTA	10.1016/j.cca.2020.07.002
YES	CLINICA CHIMICA ACTA	10.1016/j.cca.2020.08.008
YES	PEERJ	10.7717/peerj.10038
YES	JOURNAL OF MEDICAL VIROLOGY	10.1002/jmv.26365
YES	BMC ORAL HEALTH	10.1186/s12903-020-01187-3